

Holistic approach to the invasion of olive by the pathogen *Xylella fastidiosa* in the Mediterranean Basin

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Key words: ecosystem analysis, physiologically based demographic models, invasive species, geographic distribution, relative abundance.

Abstract

The Mediterranean Basin is increasingly challenged by invasive species, with the bacterial pathogen Xylella fastidiosa recently detected in olive in southern Italy being simply another one. Xylella is a major threat for organic and sustainable olive culture in the Mediterranean Basin where olive plays a vital ecological and socioeconomic role. Xylella is limited to the xylem system of plants from where it is transmitted by xylem-sap feeding insects. The olive/Xylella system is extremely complex and difficult to assess and manage because virtually all insects that feed on xylem sap are potential vectors of Xylella, and because the bacteria can be hosted by a very broad range of plants that can carry the bacteria without showing symptoms of disease. An additional layer of complexity is climate change that will affect differently each component of the olive/Xylella system. Such complexity requires development of a holistic analysis based on the ecological requirements for growth, survival and reproduction of olive, Xylella, its vectors and their natural enemies so as to determine the potential geographic distribution, abundance, and impact of this disease. The present paper illustrates how a holistic analysis could be developed for the olive/Xylella system using physiologically based demographic models (PBDMs) to assess and manage the disease on a regional basis. PBDMs build on the idea that all organisms in all trophic levels are consumers with resource acquisition processes having similar shapes described by the same mathematical functions, and with analogous allocation priorities. These analogies enable PBDMs to capture relevant ecosystem complexity at all trophic levels using a modest number of measurable parameters. In a previous analysis, PBDMs were developed for the glassy-winged sharpshooter (GWSS; Homalodisca vitripennis) that vectors X. fastidiosa causing Pierce's disease in grape in California, and for two egg parasitoids introduced for GWSS control. The model predicted that the potential range of X. fastidiosa is considerably less than that of GWSS, and that with biological control of GWSS the potential range of the pathogen was reduced still further to the desert regions of southern California. PBDM analysis was able to separate and quantify the biotic and abiotic factors that affect the distribution and abundance of X. fastidiosa in grape at the geographic scale of California, and is expected to achieve comparable results for X. fastidiosa in olive at the scale of the Mediterranean Basin.

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Introduction

The Mediterranean Basin is challenged by a growing number of exotic invasive species, with the bacterial pathogen *Xylella fastidiosa* being simply another one. The bacterium is widespread in the Americas and has been on Europe's quarantine list since 1981 (Stokstad 2015). *Xylella fastidiosa* was detected in olive in the Mediterranean Basin in the Italian region of Apulia in 2013 (Saponari et al. 2013). *Xylella* is a threat of utmost importance for organic and sustainable olive culture with most of the management focus currently on chemical (insecticides) and mechanical (soil tillage) control of vectors. This disease is currently the subject of a controversial eradication program involving destruction of infected olive trees, this despite that numerous plants host the disease and several vectors transmit the disease.

Xylella fastidiosa is limited to the xylem system of plants from where it is transmitted by xylem-sap feeding insects (Purcell 1997). It causes Pierce's disease in grape and scorch-like diseases in other plants such as citrus and olive. Virtually all insects that feed on xylem sap are potential vectors of *X. fastidiosa*, and there are tens of candidate vectors in the Mediterranean region (Bosco et al. 2014). The bacteria can be hosted by a very broad range of plants including cultivated and wild species, and plants can carry the bacteria without showing symptoms of disease (Hopkins 1989; Janse and Obradovic 2010). This makes the olive/*Xylella* system extremely complex and difficult to assess and manage, particularly in the Mediterranean Basin – a region where significantly stronger than average climate change is expected (Giorgi 2006), and where olive plays a vital role in maintaining the rich natural and agricultural biodiversity (Ponti et al. 2014; Ponti et al. 2015b).

A holistic analysis based on the ecological requirements for growth, survival and reproduction of olive, *X. fastidiosa*, its vectors and their natural enemies is required to determine the potential geographic distribution, abundance, and impact of this disease. A holistic analysis is required because the regional pest status of a species (native or exotic) depends on biotic (e.g., natural enemies) and abiotic (e.g., weather) factors (Andrewartha and Birch 1954; Larcher 1995; Wellington et al. 1999; Walther et al. 2002) that are often difficult to separate and quantify on a geographic scale (see e.g., Gutierrez et al. 1974), and this is especially true for the olive/*Xylella* system due to its multiple layers of complexity that is compounded by climate change. Regardless of system complexity, however, assessing the regional pest status of a species is the cornerstone of any regional plan for its management (Kogan 1998), and should be a prerequisite for establishing a plan for regional control on scientific grounds (see Ponti et al. 2015c). The present paper illustrates how a holistic analysis could be developed for the olive/*Xylella* system using physiologically based demographic models (PBDMs) once the necessary biological data base is assembled using PBDMs as a guideline for addressing data gaps (see Gutierrez and Ponti 2013; Ponti et al. 2015a).

Materials and methods

The underlying assumption of PBDMs is that all organisms in all trophic levels, including the economic one, are consumers that have similar resource acquisition (inputs) and allocation (outputs) priorities (Gutierrez et al. 1994; Gutierrez 1996; Regev et al. 1998). Based on analogies, the dynamics of say olive and olive fly (an important crop-pest system in the Mediterranean Basin; see Ponti et al. 2014) can be captured using the same resource acquisition and birth-death rates sub-models imbedded in an age-mass structured population model (i.e., the PBDM). Resource acquisition (i.e., the supply, S) is a search process driven by organism demand (D),

wile allocation occurs in priority order to egestion, conversion costs, respiration, and reproduction, growth, and reserves. The ratio S/D is greater or equal to zero but always lower than unity due to imperfect consumer search, and in the model scales maximal growth rates of the species in a time-place varying manner. At high resource levels, S/D tends to unity. The model for olive is a canopy model with subunit populations of leaves, stem, root, and healthy and attacked fruit. The model simulates the age-mass structured population dynamics of plant subunits and of olive fly numbers (Gutierrez et al. 2009). The olive model predicts flowering phenology controlled by vernalization, the age-structured dynamics of growth and yield, and fruit mortality due to temperature and fly attack. Olive fly biology is closely linked to olive fruit phenology, age and abundance. The effects of temperature on vital rates of olive fruit and the fly are captured by normalized concave scalar functions that approximates the net of S corrected for metabolic costs across temperature (Gutierrez et al. 2009).

Analogies enable PBDMs to capture relevant ecosystem complexity at all trophic levels using a modest number of measurable parameters (Gutierrez 1996). As the underlying functions are known (Gutierrez and Ponti 2013), parameter estimation is easier: this is a significant advantage in case the required set of sound biological data is not fully available (Ponti et al. 2015a) as it may be the case for the olive/*Xylella* system in the Mediterranean Basin.

A previous PBDM analysis of the grape/*Xylella* system in California (Gutierrez et al. 2011) provides a methodological template for developing a regional assessment of the olive/*Xylella* system in the Mediterranean Basin. In California, the PBDM approach was used to analyze the geographic distribution and relative abundance (i.e., measures of invasiveness) of the polyphagous glassy-winged sharpshooter (GWSS; *Homalodisca vitripennis*), a pest native to the southeastern United States and northeastern Mexico that extended its range into California in 1989. GWSS vectors *X. fastidiosa* that causes Pierce's disease in grape. PBDMs for GWSS and its two egg parasitoids *Gonatocerus ashmeadi* and *G. triguttatus* were developed and linked to a published PBDM for grape. A temperature-dependent rate model for *X. fastidiosa* was also developed. Daily weather data from 108 locations across California for the period 1995-2006 were used to drive the PBDM simulation. Further methodological details can be found in Gutierrez et al. (2011) and references cited therein.

A PBDM for the olive/*Xylella* system, once developed and when driven by appropriate daily weather data, enables not only simulation of the multi trophic system dynamics across the Mediterranean Basin but also mapping of these dynamics via a geographic information system (GIS; e.g. GRASS GIS, see <http://grass.osgeo.org/>).

Results and Discussion

The capacity to measure the invasiveness of *X. fastidiosa* by predicting its geographic distribution and relative abundance is pivotal to developing policy for its eradication or control and management (Gutierrez et al. 2011). This capacity must involve holistic analysis based on the different ecological requirements for growth, survival and reproduction of the host plant (e.g., olive), *X. fastidiosa*, its vectors and their natural enemies. Holistic analysis is a must because it is all of the key component species of the host plant/*Xylella* system that by interacting with weather and with each other determine as a whole (cf. holistic) the potential geographic distribution, abundance, and impact of the disease.

Demographic physiologically based models (i.e., PBDMs) that provide a capacity for assessing the invasiveness of *X. fastidiosa* were developed in a previous analysis for California where the bacterium is vectored by the invasive insect GWSS and causes Pierce's disease in grape (Gutierrez et al. 2011). Modeling the olive/*Xylella* system in the Mediterranean Basin can take advantage of both the holistic analysis of the grape/*Xylella* system in California as a template (Gutierrez et al. 2011) and the existing PBDM for olive as a basis (Gutierrez et al. 2009). The resulting PBDM for the olive/*Xylella* system can be used to develop sustainable management strategies and tactics to address the disease on a regional basis.

In California, the predicted geographic range of the invasive GWSS accorded well with field observations that this vector of *X. fastidiosa* is largely restricted to the warmer southern areas of the state. The action of the egg parasitoids introduced for biological control of GWSS was predicted to reduce vector abundance more than 90%. The geographic range of *X. fastidiosa* was predicted to be the warmer inland areas of southern California, with biological control of GWSS decreasing this range further. Analysis of climate warming scenarios suggested the distribution and severity of GWSS and *X. fastidiosa* would increase in the agriculturally rich Central Valley of California.

In essence, the model predicted that the potential range of *X. fastidiosa* is considerably less than that of GWSS, and that with biological control of GWSS the potential range of the pathogen was reduced still further to the desert regions of southern California. PBDM analysis was able to separate and quantify the biotic and abiotic factors that affect the distribution and abundance of *X. fastidiosa* in grape at the geographic scale of California, and is expected to achieve comparable results for *X. fastidiosa* in olive at the scale of the Mediterranean Basin.

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